

Figure Z13

Figure Z13: Cell-state and cell-type-specific transcriptomic changes for top pathways regulated by high-fat diet and exercise training in vWAT. (A and B) Cell-state-specific (A) and cell-type-specific (B) DEGs and their membership in significantly enriched pathways: sample-specific mean expression for each gene (left heatmap), their fold changes in the three comparisons whenever available (middle heatmap, * if significant), and their membership in the pathways (right heatmap). A list of abbreviations used in this figure appear in the Methods.